

INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF SCREW COMPRESSORS USED IN INDUSTRY

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ABSTRACT

Increasing energy efficiency is the most important energy source today. Therefore, the main success criterion of product development studies is seen as efficiency. Compressors; It is widely used in many different sectors, especially petro-chemical, electronics, automotive, food, machinery, glass, machining, textile, construction. In our daily life, compressors are among the indispensable main components in refrigerators we use at home and in transportation (bus, train, truck). To put it in a nutshell, while people need air to live, the operation of industry depends on compressed air. Compressed air requirement is provided by compressors without alternatives. According to research, approximately 10% of industrial energy consumption in Europe and Australia is used for compressed air production. However, the energy consumed for the production of compressed air in some sectors in the USA reaches up to 30% of the total energy consumed. These studies have shown that the compressors used for the production of compressed air in the industry are the main machines that cause energy consumption. Therefore, energy efficiency in compressors is one of the main criteria for the industry.

When the screw compressor development studies are examined in the literature, the main working area is to increase the efficiency of the compressor and reduce the operating costs. This study covers the parametric optimization of the components that affect the performance of an oil type screw compressor with a one-dimensional thermodynamic model, using RSO (Response Surface Optimization Technique) and Taguchi optimization techniques, which are widely preferred in the literature. Stosic et al. investigated the performance of the rotor profile tooth depth on the compressor in their study. The outer diameter of the female rotor and the distance between the rotors, which affect the rotor tooth depth, were also investigated parametrically.

When drilling wells in a productive formation being penetrated, hydrostatic bottomhole pressure when it rises above the formation pressure may cause absorption of the drilling fluid by the formation, and when the formation pressure rises above the bottomhole pressure created by the mud column, then fluids enter the well and this can create a blowout, i.e. a manifestation; and absorption and manifestation are accidents.

Losses of the solution result in a decrease in hydrostatic pressure on the well wall in the upper part of the well body, cleaning occurs and favorable business is formed, including the violation of the zone around the well body; which lead to the extraction of the drilling tool and its sticking; therefore, in order to eliminate loss, it is necessary to reduce the density of the drilling fluid, if possible, and increase the value of the structural viscosity. Most accidents occur when drilling clayey rocks.

To reduce the adhesion of clay cake on the well wall, special chemicals are added to the solution: CMAD-1, graphite, oil, sulfonol, OII-10, CAM, soapstock tar (ST).

The narrowing of the well body occurs as a result of swelling of the clay layers.

To prevent complications and accidents associated with the drill string, they are systematically pressure tested. Test pressure values for different depths are shown.

To eliminate accidents associated with the drill bit, it cannot be kept at the bottom of the well for a long time.

The article presents the formulas:

- to determine the maximum speed of descent of the drilling tool.
- to determine the density of the solution.
- to determine the minimum stock of drilling fluid

The wellhead is equipped with appropriate preventers [1].

When the hydrostatic pressure at the well bottom rises above the formation pressure in the opened productive formation during the drilling of the wells, an accident of drilling fluid absorption into the formation may occur. Or, when the formation pressure rises above the bottom pressure caused by the mud column in the wellbore, oil, gas, and water may be forced from the formation into the wellbore, causing a jump in the drilled well, i.e., an occurrence event. Both of events can be accidents or sometimes disasters.

Absorption of drilling fluid through the formation results in a drop in hydrostatic pressure at the wellbore wall and stripping of the upper part of the wellbore, creating favorable conditions for gas, oil, and water jumps, as well as disruption of the wellbore zone, which can lead to pulling or trapping of the drilling tool. takes out; therefore, in order to prevent absorption, it is required to reduce the density of the drilling fluid as much as possible and to increase the structural viscosity.

Keywords: compressor, screw compressor, HAD, RSO, Taguchi, rotor, modernization, energy efficiency, technologies.

Introduction. Screw compressors are the most widely used compressors in industry and practice, and the rotor part of these compressors is completely imported or the compressor is imported entirely. Screw compressors consist of two nested helical rotors called

male and female. The bulging part of the male rotor is called the lobe, while the cavity of the female rotor corresponding to this lobe is called the groove. The gas used as the working fluid in compressors is air. The compressor pressurizes the air with the shrinking

volume between the rotors by compressing the air between the rotors and the rest it has outside. The operation of the screw block can be explained in 4 phases. In the 1st phase, air is taken between the rotors from the suction port. In the 2nd and 3rd phases, the air filled between the rotors starts to compress as the rotors rotate in opposite directions. In the last phase, the compressed air is discharged through the discharge port. This step repeats itself according to the rotor lobe configuration.

Let's talk about the structure of the screw block. The rotor pair placed in the body is supported by bearings. These bearings are lubricated with pressurized oil pressurized by the compressor. While the rotor pair can be driven by the male rotor in oil-injected screw compressors, the male and female rotors can also be driven by a gear in dry type compressors.

The air is filtered from the suction port by the air inlet filter and taken to the screw block. After the air is mixed with oil in the screw block, the compressed oil-air mixture is sent to the oil tank. The air-oil mixture is sent from the oil tank to the air/oil separator to separate the air and oil. The separated compressed air is cooled in the radiator and offered for use. The oil separated from the air is passed through the thermostatic valve

and directed to the radiator or the oil tank depending on the temperature. Thus, the compressor cycle is ensured.

Kinematic analysis of screw compressor. The most important parameters in determining the performance of the screw compressor are the geometric parameters that make up the rotor. In the compressor design, the lobe combination is selected depending on the type, usage area and usage conditions of the compressor. Today, the ratio of male/female lobes 4/6 is widely used for the same outer diameter. This lobe combination can be preferred in all compressor processes, including dry and oily type. But in use, combinations of 5/6, 5/7, 4/5, 3/5 are also becoming more and more common. Male rotors with 5/6 or 5/7 lobe ratios can reach higher compression ratios thanks to the high helix angle. 4/5 ratio is preferred in oil type compressors where the compression ratio is slightly lower. High cycle rate is recommended for dry type compressors. Therefore, 3/5 lobe combination is used in dry type compressors. Compressor rotor is formed depending on the section profile, helix angle, distance between rotors, rotor outer diameter and rotor length, which are optimized according to the determined lobe configuration of the rotor.

Geometric terminology based on rotor profile.

Another geometric parameter in screw compressors defines the ports. Port opening angles and surface areas are another input parameter in one-dimensional thermodynamic calculations. Two surface areas, axial and radial, are defined for the suction and discharge port. There is a single port area for the oil port. The opening of the ports is defined according to the rotation angle of the male rotor. The lobe diagram is determined according to the position of the male rotor lobe and the female rotor groove at the determined opening angle. The position of the oil injection port is determined according to the opening angle. This position is determined by the injected oil temperature and the air temperature at the

injection point. Since the most important purpose in lubrication is to provide thermal control of the compressor, the oil temperature entering the compressor cannot be higher than the air temperature at the location of the lubrication port.

Fat injection. The main purpose of oil injection in compressors is to provide thermal control inside the compressor. At the same time, the film layer formed on the rotor prevents dry friction between the rotors and minimizes leakage losses by reducing the gap between the rotors. The injected oil flow rate is calculated with the orifice approach. Oil supply to the compressor can be via a separate pump or by self-lubrication of the

compressor with the pressure obtained from the compressor. Screw compressors are commonly lubricated by their own pressure. In this context, the pressure at the outlet of the screw compressor constitutes the boundary condition for the oil.

Leakage streams. Leakage losses in the compressor are one of the most important parameters that affect the volumetric efficiency of the compressor. In order to reduce compressor leakage losses, it is aimed to reduce the gaps between the rotors around the contact line and the gaps between the rotor and the stator. In this context, the cross-sectional parameters of the rotor and the parameters defining the 3rd dimension constitute the geometric parameters of the interrotor space. In the compressor, each volume between the lobe of the male rotor and the groove of the female rotor constitutes a flow volume. In other words, the lobe and groove form the flow volume limit. Each defined flow volume tends to pass into the low pressure flow volume through the interrotor and rotor-stator spaces. Because of this tendency, leakage losses occur in the compressor. Leakage flows constantly circulate between the compressor rotors and create the mass difference between inlet and

outlet. This mass difference defines the amount of leakage loss.

There are leakages between the rotors at the line where the outer sweeping circle of the rotors intersect. This line is defined on both sides, the suction and the discharge side. The gaps between the rotors formed in these regions create the leakages between the rotors. The main purpose of profile approaches is to increase efficiency by reducing these gaps. As a matter of fact, the most important advantage of the "N" profile used is that it minimizes these gaps. Achieving the ultimate goal of increasing volumetric efficiency depends on the parametric definition of these voids.

Optimization of screw compressor. The performance of screw compressors is highly dependent on the male and female rotor profiles. Within the scope of this study, optimization studies will be carried out on the basic profile. The most important advantage of optimization over the basic profile is the creation of male and female rotors over a single reference profile. Thus, the lower shear limits in the male and female rotor profiles can be determined, and there is no adaptation problem between the rotors.

First, the "N" profile developed by Stosic and the basic (rack) profile created by Yu Ren Wu et al. were parametricized. Stosic et al. investigated the performance of the rotor profile tooth depth on the compressor in their study. Therefore, the optimization parameters affecting the rotor tooth depth; The outer diameter of the rotors and the distance between the rotors are also included parametrically. The performance of the parameters was calculated using SCORG, MATLAB; The profile is optimized with RSO and Taguchi optimization techniques. These two different optimization results used were compared. Body side optimization for the selected optimized profile was made with the RSO method. In the body side optimization, the opening angle of the ports and the oil injection position are determined.

In RSO and Taguchi optimization techniques, variations (design sets) were produced within the specified number and limits of parameters. The rotor profile is optimized for the objective functions determined by these variations. The variations obtained by using the parameters determined for the RSO method are produced with the ANSYS optimization tool and, xls file is converted. Rotor profile coordinate file is created with MATLAB for each variation. Thermodynamic results are calculated using SCORG as a solvent in the background. This cycle continues until all variations are completed. The resulting file is used for the optimization tool and optimized parameters are obtained for the determined objective function.

MATLAB was used to define the optimization parameters to SCORG for the Demonstrated "N" profile, which is the profile developed by Stosic, and the rotor profiles were created by SCORG.

SCORG has been used for both geometric and one-dimensional thermodynamic calculations as well as meshing for CFX.

Optimization with RSO optimization method.

RSO is a multi-objective optimization technique in which the best possible designs are derived from a sample set, taking into account the goals or constraints we have set for the parameters. The optimization approaches used in the RSO optimization technique can be listed as follows:

- Screening
- MOGA
- NLPQL
- MISQP
- Adaptive Single-Objective
- Adaptive Multiple-Objective

Within the scope of this study, the MOGA approach was preferred in order to include multiple objective functions in the optimization.

This optimization technique consists of two main stages. The first stage is the design research and the second stage is the optimization stage. For the variation (design set) determined in the RSO method; First of all, a design research is conducted in order to determine the effect factor on the determined objective function. Design research is an approach used by DesignXplorer to design and understand the analysis response of design. Design of Experiments (DOE) uses a deterministic method based on and various optimization techniques with parameters as key components. Responses are workable, measurable, and graphable. By using a goal-based optimization technique, it can achieve multiple design points in the deterministic method. In addition, the calculated response surface can be examined and can generate design points directly from the surface.

Oil injection point and discharge port optimization. Within the scope of port optimization; Parametric optimization of the design parameters of the suction, discharge and injection ports was made by the RSO method. Optimization of two parameters is aimed for oil injection point and port optimization. These are the oil injection point and the opening angle of the discharge port.

Port designs. The volume referenced in port design and in determining the location of the oil injection port is the location of the flow volume between the rotors. In other words, in the position where the male rotor is at 0° , the region between the lobe and the groove with the highest flow volume is taken as a reference. While defining the oil injection port according to the position of the flow volume obtained by the rotation of the male rotor, the discharge port is designed according to the cross-section design of the flow volume of the rotor at the relevant rotation angle. All operating conditions of the compressor are defined according to the rotation angle of the male rotor. This rotation angle continues until the working volume is completed in the female rotor process. As a matter of fact, this process is completed at different angles for different rotor configurations. The rotor profile section referenced in the suction port design is the section of the rotor profile that reaches the highest flow volume. Thus, the suction port section expands from the minimum volume of the flow

volume in the axial direction and continues the suction process up to the maximum volume it reaches.

Optimization with RSO. The RSO technique used in rotor optimization was made by taking the optimized Nine Curved "N" profile as reference. Taguchi technique, which is another optimization technique used in rotor optimization, will not be used in port optimization within the scope of this study. The most important reason for this is that the number of parameters required for the design set to be created is limited to 2. As a matter of fact, Taguchi's most important advantage, which is the reduction of the number of variations with orthogonal sequences, is not applicable for a small number of parameters.

Computational fluid dynamics (CFD) Creating the model. Computational fluid dynamics (CFD) is used in many different fields, from industrial applications to academic research. Although CFD was initially famous only in aerospace high-tech engineering applications, it is now widely used for solving complex problems encountered in modern engineering applications. The most important advantage of computational simulations is that they function as a "virtual laboratory". Thus, design development and optimization costs were reduced; Design processes are shortened. Today, CFD has become one of the most effective methods used to solve fluid dynamics and heat transfer problems.

In CFD analysis, the volume in which the dynamic or static state of the flow is defined and the analysis is made is called the flow volume or the calculation volume. CFD analyzes are performed by iterative analysis of partial differential equations by dividing the generated flow volume into physical volumes called solution mesh.

In this study, ANSYS CFX package software was used for CFD analysis. In this section, first of all, the creation of boundary conditions, the results and the comparison of the results with the SCORG results will be examined.

Creating flow volume. The rotor geometry, which defines the limits of the flow volume of screw compressors, rotates in time and a different flow volume occurs at each time step. Such flow volumes are called dynamic flow volumes. Modeling dynamic flow volumes is the most challenging part. In screw compressors, the inlet port, discharge port and oil injection port represent the stator side of the compressor and the rotor represents the dynamic part of the compressor.

Creating a solution network. The flow volume changes according to the time-dependent rotation of the rotors, which form the dynamic part of the screw compressors. Conventional mesh tools are used to deform the mesh and adapt the mesh. But every deformation of the solution mesh; although it reduces the quality of the mesh, it causes negative volumes. The complex geometric structure of screw compressors makes it almost impossible to dynamically create solution networks. Therefore, special mesh tools are used in screw compressors. Within the scope of this study, the mesh of the rotor was created using SCORG's mesh tool. SCORG's mesh is the determined rotation angle of the rotor; It is based on the principle of creating a solution network in

the same number of nodes according to each new flow volume for each time step defined in the determined cycle. This mesh, created in one time step, is imported by the CFD solver. For the new situation, the analysis in the previous time step is iteratively accepted as the initial condition and the analysis is done in the new time step. Thus, high quality solutions can be made with a structured solution network.

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